

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D8.2 TraceMyFish Business Plan

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ACRONYMS LIST

iFMS	Intelligent Fish Management System
B2B	Business to Business
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UN	United Nations
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
EU	European Union
USP	Unique Selling Proposition
RoHS	Restriction of Hazardous Substances
SLA	Service Level Agreement
R&D	Research and Development

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TraceMyFish Consortium aims at commercially exploiting the output of the project, the intelligent Fish Management System (iFMS), so to enhance the seafood value-chain with state-of-the-art quality control technologies.

Task 8.2 – TraceMyFish Business Plan focuses on development of a business model for the commercialization of the iFMS, which will be implemented for the exploitation of the project’s outputs.

This deliverable initially presents the iFMS as the combination of technologies from the two industrial consortium partners: Videometer and Scio. The two firms contribute to the project by providing and developing respectively spectral imaging instruments with their related software – the VideometerLab, VideometerLite and the VideometerLab Software with Cloud Workspaces – and a data-management platform for the tracking of seafood throughout the value-chain – Quantum Platform. Here, we also present the partners’ mission statements and their business to business (B2B) strategies for the pricing and positioning of their products.

Task 8.2’s results are hereby presented and described in detail. The deliverable, in fact, illustrates the results of an in-depth industry analysis, with trends coming into life, risks that may be encountered and mitigation plans. We present an accurate account of the Unique Selling Proposition (USP), that present the iFMS’ competitive advantage compared to substitutes in the industry.

The second section of the deliverable focuses on the role of sustainability and the strategy determined for ensuring a responsible product. Here, we take into account both the concept of circular economy for a sustainable manufacturing of the VideometerLite instrument and the United Nation’s (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the potential impact the iFMS has on said targets.

Finally, we present a Marketing plan in the form of the Marketing Mix model and the concluding Business Model Canvas for the system, showcasing a complete and detailed strategy for the commercialization of the iFMS.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aiming at advancing the blue bioeconomy supply system, the TraceMyFish project implements an intelligent Fish Management System (iFMS) capable of tracking and tracing safety and quality of seafood products throughout their value chains.

Workpackage 8, which was carried out throughout the whole duration of the project (November 1st, 2021, to October 31st, 2023), focused on the business strategies tailored to the economic exploitation of the project. In particular, **Workpackage Task 8.1 Market Analysis and Uptake Strategy** aimed at assessing the market and industry for the further development, in **Workpackage Task 8.2 TraceMyFish Business Plan**, of a tangible and measurable B2B Strategy.

Workpackage Task 8.2 TraceMyFish Business Plan, specifically, was carried out between months 10 (August 2022) and 24 (October 2023). During this period, the focus was set on assessing the forces that influence the industry in terms of trends, risks and mitigations and the positioning and pricing strategy which would best suit the iFMS. Furthermore, a detailed analysis on sustainable manufacturing processes and product life-cycle management was carried out, in order to ensure a long-lasting and responsible business strategy.

Partners involved in this Workpackage were the two industrial constituents: SCiO and Videometer, each bringing their technical infrastructure and expertise towards building the iFMS, the final outcome of the project.

2 B2B STRATEGY

2.1 VISION AND MISSION STATEMENTS

A tangible B2B Strategy, which takes into account achievable and measurable goals, sets its fundamentals in the direction a firm is aiming to take. For this reason, throughout the investigation and development of the B2B strategy, we took into account the Vision and Mission Statements of the two industrial partners: SCiO and Videometer, and the overall TraceMyFish project as a consortium.

SCiO's vision for the iFMS falls under its general ambition to provide services that maximize the value of an organization's data and provide meaningful, actionable analytics for variegating use cases. To achieve this, a broad range of services, scientific, technical, and business-oriented must be employed to support scientists and enterprises on their data-driven endeavors. As such, SCiO's mission statements culminates in ***the provision of multi-faceted support for transforming data to true societal, financial and environmental impact.***

Videometer's ***aims at ensuring optimal production process and documented product integrity throughout supply chains in different industries with spectral imaging, machine learning and AI, image processing and cloud technologies.*** As a company focusing on quality control, Videometer values and takes responsibility for promoting sustainable practices that enhance safety throughout the different industries, such as the seafood value chain.

The overall TraceMyFish mission combines the goals and values of all partners in the TraceMyFish consortium with the aim of ***advancing the supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing an intelligent Fish Management System, that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains.***

2.2 FINAL PRODUCT

Task 8.2 takes into account the iFMS as the combination of technologies developed by Videometer A/S and SCiO Systems.

SCiO contributes by developing:

- Quantum: an AI-driven platform that aids agri-food organizations in generating value from their data.

Videometer A/S contributes with the further development of:

1. VideometerLab: Videometer’s flagship spectral imaging devices, capturing high resolution images for the analysis of different products.
2. VideometerLite: a handheld and wireless spectral imaging device.
3. VideometerLab Software including Cloud Workspaces: virtual locations, which allow for the methodical storing, managing and sharing of data.

Figure 1 shows how these technologies will be integrated for the iFMS to function properly.

Figure 1 Configuration of the intelligent Fish Management System (iFMS)

The envisioned final iFMS product entails the technologies and interfaces that will allow the setup, deployment and usage of a bespoke platform version tailored to the specific data problems of the client. The process entails the analysis of the data to understand pre-processing and ingestion requirements, the training of the AI models solving the data problems of the client, and finally their integration on the computational platform. The entire cycle is supported via the appropriate configuration and deployment of a Quantum instance. Quantum is a platform capable of gathering, harmonizing, and integrating heterogeneous data from different sources to support AI-powered analytics for facilitating decision making in Food Systems. Quantum is based on the microservices architecture, designed and implemented following an event-driven paradigm. Consequently, Quantum is a collection of services that communicate to each other by submitting and/or consuming events from a cluster of message brokers. This ensures that the services are loosely coupled, easily maintainable

testable, and updatable, and can be deployed independently. Quantum allows fast end-to-end processing, more reliable update of existing services, easy addition of new services and rapid yet reliable delivery of end-to-end complex and large applications.

In the case of the TraceMyFish iFMS, Quantum can be connected to the Videometer cloud to ingest and process data collected across the value chain and enact the appropriate models for analysing them. Analytical results and data history are presented to the users via the relevant interfaces, depending on each user's access levels.

The VideometerLite is based on Videometer's spectral imaging technology. Spectral imaging is a scientific methodology which combines imaging with spectroscopy, allowing for the measurement of different spectra within the same image (Carstensen, 2018)

Spectral imaging, in the Videometer case, is achieved by placing a camera on the top of an integrating sphere, with LEDs of different wavelengths placed around its equator. The integrating sphere comprises of a hollow sphere with a highly reflective coating, which allows for uniformity in the scattering and diffusing effects of the LEDs' light rays (Figure 1). The LEDs strobe sequentially to capture a stack of images recorded at different wavelengths. Consequently, each pixel in the captured image represents a reflectance spectrum. The range of the Videometer technology includes ultraviolet, visual, and near-infrared wavelengths. Additionally, fluorescence can be captured by placing different filters in front of the camera. (Carstensen & Folm-Hansen, 2006).

Videometer's flagship instrument, the VideometerLab, captures images with up to 20 different wavelengths ranging from 365 nm to 970 nm and four additional fluorescence bands. The VideometerLite instrument, on the other hand, is developed to capture images with an array of 12 wavelengths ranging between 365 nm to 850 nm and three additional fluorescence bands.

Videometer's technology further develops on its spectral imaging methodology by combining it with a machine learning, AI, and cloud-driven software for accurate and comprehensive analysis of the images taken. Both instruments come with the VideometerLab Software, which, besides offering image visualization, allows the user to perform advanced image analysis and processing. Among others, the platform implements algorithms for transforming and segmenting images, for automatic recognition of sample features and for model building. The VideometerLab Software includes the Videometer Cloud Workspaces, virtual locations which allow the users to store, manage and share their data with their stakeholders.

2.3 SALES MODEL: PRICING AND POSITIONING

As mentioned previously, the TraceMyFish consortium includes two industrial partners: SCiO and Videometer. The two partners develop separate elements of the iFMS, with SCiO focusing on data analysis, models and algorithms with the Quantum Platform, and Videometer focusing on the development of the spectral imaging instrument – the VideometerLite for data capturing.

The two elements have separate sales models with distinguished pricing and positioning strategies, based on the needs of the company itself. The models are summarized in the following sections.

2.3.1 SCiO's Model

- User contacts SCiO sales to establish their interest and describe their data problem
- SCiO designs and provides cost estimates for pre-processing customization requirements
- User provides sample data for initial training / configuration of the ML models
- Trained models are integrated in Quantum deployment
- Users are being provided with access to the platform via their preferred licensing scheme
 - Yearly subscription
 - Layered pricing according to data ingested / calls to the predictive service
 - Additional development hours for continuous support / customization

SCiO will build and offer a set of technical and consulting services over the iFMS. The services include support and consultation on data problems, and specifically the analysis of data requirements and data processing required to serve the specific data problems. Furthermore, another branch of services is the development of custom models for each use case and the provision of SLAs for their re-training when necessary. Finally, SCiO can provide managed hosting services for the entire platform to ensure optimisation of computational resources usage as well as data security and integrity.

For purely consulting services, the pricing model will be based on the consulting hours required from data managers and scientists to setup the use case. Development time will also be charged on an hourly basis for customisations on the interface if required by the client. Analytical reports will be provided under a subscription scheme, with the frequency and length of report production determining the price of the offering.

On the other hand, hosting services will also incorporate costs for infrastructure usage and maintenance. Different packages, usage-based or subscription-based can be formed, while special agreements for large scale contracts will be arranged on a case-by-case basis.

2.3.2 Videometer's Model

- The user accesses the Videometer webshop: shop.videometer.com, creates an account and navigates to the VideometerLite Package page. This includes:
 - A VideometerLite with First Year Subscription Plan.
 - VideometerLite Software annual license including global workspaces.
 - One cloud workspace with 100GB storage – additional data packages of 100GB can be purchased separately on the webshop.
 - One blue background plate
 - One white calibration plate
 - One battery
 - Ethernet cable
- The user can eventually purchase VideometerLite add-ons on the webshop. The add-ons comprise of:
 - Liquid add-on (VideometerLite Liq) – a mount for the instrument which allows the image capturing of flasks/bottles with liquid samples.
 - Replacement calibration plates.
 - Replacement background plates (blue, red, green, or color of choice).
 - Customizations based on customer needs at extra price.

In the course of the TraceMyFish project, Videometer has developed the Videometer webshop, in order to allow users with a smooth and rapid buying experience. The instrument and data packages for the cloud workspaces are sold at a cost-efficient price, supporting the purchase by all players in the seafood value chain and can be delivered rapidly to the customer. In fact, the data packages can be delivered in a maximum of one business day, while the VideometerLite instrument has a consignment time of 3-4 business weeks.

2.4 USERS

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and document analyses performed during task 8.1 Market Analysis and Uptake Strategy, it was possible to understand who the iFMS users will be and how they will interact with the system. Based on how the supply chain is structured and what has been mentioned by the respondents of the interviews, the user personas can be segmented in four groups:

- Researchers and R&D Professionals
- Seafood Processing Professionals
- Harvesters
- Retailers

In this section, we will describe each of the segments.

Researchers and R&D Professionals: This first segment includes highly educated professionals who work in laboratory settings. These individuals are used to using advanced laboratory equipment for their daily processes. They are responsible for research design and have the need to collect data in different contexts and with different instruments for the validation of their studies. At the moment, these individuals perceive only being capable of collecting data in-lab as a limitation to their work. Furthermore, they believe laboratory contexts often lack automation, which could help relieve them from hefty manual work, thus increasing efficiency. An additional pain point the researchers incur is the fact that data sharing with stakeholder can be complicated to achieve. In fact, often it is nearly impossible to share data and results with external entities to their organizations.

Seafood Processing Professionals: Processing professionals are individuals who perform highly manual tasks in factory settings. Their work includes manually assessing the seafood's quality either on-line or in-line. These activities are quite timely and subjective, allowing for misinterpretations due to human errors. Moreover, some hazards are difficult to detect with the naked eye only, like, for example, parasites or bones. The time-consuming processes translate in slower decision-making activities that are based on the seafood's quality, which can be an inconvenience in enterprises that perform multiple operations. Finally, these individuals need to ensure full transparency of their seafood's data (provenience, batch number, etc.) to fully guarantee high quality and maximize their prices, sales, and profits.

Harvesters: Harvesters often operate for the same companies of the processing professionals. This segment, though, is made up of professionals mainly working on fishing fleets. Just like the processing professionals, the harvesters need to quickly assess the quality of their seafood for decision-making activities. Harvesters, as well, need to ensure the transparency and the safety of their data, in order to guarantee the high standards of their product and be able to maximize their profits.

Retailers: Retailers operate in-market. They're objective is that of avoiding seafood fraud with unlabelled or wrongly labelled species. Moreover, they also have the need of assessing the quality and transparency of their seafood in order to guarantee high standards.

3 EMERGING TRENDS IN THE SEAFOOD INDUSTRY

International communities, such as the United Nations (UN), and European Union (EU) are setting focus on the need for transformative actions across food systems, in order to ensure safe, nutritious, sustainable and equitable food for the globe.

Among the actions taken by the UN is the publication of the Food and Agriculture Organization's (FAO,2021) Roadmap for Blue Transformation, in which the institution sets the targets, goals and timeframes for a series of transformative actions throughout the seafood value chain and defines Blue Transformation as “a targeted effort by which agencies, countries and dependent communities, use existing and emerging knowledge, tools and practices to secure and sustainably maximize the contribution of aquatic (both marine and inland) food systems to food security, nutrition and affordable healthy diets for all.” (FAO, 2021:2)

Among the relevant objectives for the TraceMyFish consortium is that of helping develop “upgraded value chains ensure the social, economic and environmental viability of aquatic food systems.” (FAO, 2021:20), which includes actions points addressing the need for existing and emerging technologies to enhance the seafood value chain operations for sustainable practices, such as waste-management, traceability and more.

According to a 2021 Ernst Young Group report on Industrial Trends within the Icelandic and Norwegian Seafood Industries (EYG, 2021), there is still large unrealized potential within the seafood industry when it comes to implementing data-driven technologies for the upgrading of the value chain. This is especially true for cloud, AI and wireless/portable technologies, which will aid the industry in creating sustainable value by, for example, enabling waste management practices, traceability and efficiency (Gartner, 2022).

The iFMS, with its objective of **allowing the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains**, fits favorably in the transformative environment described above, proving that the system could be beneficial to users across the seafood value chain, in order to enhance their operations and practices, both in terms of sustainability and of innovativeness.

4 RISKS AND MITIGATIONS

The implementation of the iFMS could herald a significant step forward in the seafood industry's digital transformation. However, like any innovation, it is not without its inherent risks. To ensure a smooth adoption and maximize the system's benefits, it's crucial to acknowledge and mitigate these potential challenges.

4.1 RISKS

- The seafood industry has a long history and is often characterized by traditional practices, which can breed reluctance towards adopting digital innovations.
- The market for cloud-based e-monitoring systems is becoming increasingly competitive, with potential substitutes and alternatives vying for attention.
- The inclination to keep data proprietary can be a significant hurdle to effective data sharing and cooperation among industry stakeholders.

4.2 MITIGATION

- It's important to understand that the seafood industry is evolving, and companies that don't adapt and innovate risk losing their competitiveness. Engaging in the digital transformation, like adopting iFMS, is a strategic response to these changing dynamics.
- iFMS stands out by offering a complete system, encompassing not only e-monitoring, Quantum and the Videometer workspaces, but also a spectral imaging instrument, the VideometerLite and image processing software, the VideometerLab Software. Furthermore, the system is efficiently priced and affordable, making it an attractive choice for seafood companies looking to enhance their operations.
- iFMS can be positioned as an asset for the regulation of the seafood industry. It can help industry players meet regulatory requirements efficiently and provide valuable data for sustainable fisheries management.
- To address the risk of substitutes and maintain quality, a proactive approach is essential. This involves evaluating the components of the iFMS based on their life-cycle and the reliability of the suppliers, ensuring a stable and sustainable supply chain.
- The iFMS includes substantial know-how that is challenging to replicate. Emphasizing the uniqueness of the system's design and technology can dissuade potential competitors and protect the system's intellectual property.
- Demonstrating how sharing data can lead to improved sustainability, operational efficiency, and competitive advantages can ease concerns and resistance.

In conclusion, while the seafood industry presents certain risks associated with adopting the iFMS system, the mitigations in place and the system's unique features make it a compelling and valuable tool for industry stakeholders. Embracing digital transformation, highlighting the iFMS's unique selling points, and addressing

concerns regarding data-sharing are all essential steps to maximize the system's benefits and drive the seafood industry towards a more sustainable and efficient future.

5 UNIQUE SELLING PROPOSITIONS

A unique selling proposition (USP) is a concept informing customers about what distinguishes a company, product or service from those of competitors. It answers the question: “Why should clients choose this product or brand over that of competition?”.

Usually, an effective USP includes:

- Unique features and benefits of the product/brand.
- Customer pain points or needs that are satisfied through the use of the product/brand.
- Value sustained by the customer by purchasing the product.

(Grant, 2018)

In regard to the iFMS, the unique selling proposition can be summarized as follows:

“The iFMS is a cost-efficient, portable, wireless AI-driven quality and safety analysis system. The intelligent system is capable of tracking and tracing the quality and safety of seafood products throughout the whole value chain. This complete solution automates traceability and advances information richness across the blue bioeconomy, leading to more responsible and sustainable industry.”

The iFMS consists of high-quality spectral imaging devices along with software for analysis and AI-driven platforms that together aid users with faster decision-making processes. The richness of insight into the quality and safety of seafood products from the developed system aims to support stakeholders across the seafood industry. The iFMS is an attainable system for any player in the value chain due to its cost-efficiency and availability both through e-commerce, but also through traditional sales processes with a sales representative.

6 SUSTAINABILITY

The seafood industry is highly influenced by environmental factors. The growth in demand of seafood, for example, has led to environmental issues such as overfishing. For this reason, the demand for sustainable technologies, that ensure responsible practices has seen and will continue seeing an increase.

The TraceMyFish project, has aimed at developing a product embracing sustainable practices. Deliverable 8.2 includes a detailed account of the processes and assessments made, in order to ensure a tangible sustainable strategy.

6.1 RESPONSIBLE PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AND MANUFACTURING

The VideometerLite’s design put the users at the center of the process. Their needs and use cases were carefully analysed and assessed, as their extensive knowledge provided insights in the practical use of the instrument and in application areas such as microbiology, food science, hazard detection, supply chain processes, methodologies, and tools.

Figure 2 VideometerLite Design and Development Iterative Process

The iterative process incorporated knowledge and expertise from cross-functional teams, with diverse backgrounds and capabilities, including software, cloud, image processing, mechanics, optics, electronics and more. Their expertise included considerations on sustainable production and development.

6.1.1 Hardware Components

In compliance with Directive 2011/65/EU “on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment” (RoHS <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32011L0065>), the Videometer Instruments are affixed with the CE-marking, meaning that the instruments are manufactured with materials that are certified and do not contain heavy metals. This is to ensure the reduction of risks on human and environmental health related to these materials.

The VideometerLab instruments’ packaging, unless otherwise requested, is made of certified paper and carton products, specifically these materials are attested by the Forest Stewardship Council as being 100% sourced from “well-managed forests”, meaning that their production does not lead to deforestation or environmental damage.

6.1.2 Software Components

In regard to software, web and cloud components, the TraceMyFish consortium made the conscious choice to host services within the broader European Union. This deliberate decision offers several sustainable advantages: by hosting the services locally or within the EU, we significantly reduce the carbon footprint associated with data transfer and hosting. Data centers that are closer to the SCiO and Videometer base require less energy for data transmission, cutting down emissions.

Data centers and servers were chosen to be supplied by PUE (Power Usage Efficiency) certified providers (Microsoft, 2020). PUE data centers are designed to maximize energy efficiency. These facilities are equipped with advanced technologies and infrastructure that minimize energy waste, resulting in a reduced environmental impact. In summary, the sustainability of iFMS software components extends beyond the software itself. It encompasses the choice of hosting services within the EU, reducing carbon footprint, supporting stringent environmental standards, renewable energy initiatives and complying to GDPR standards.

6.2 PRODUCT LIFE-CYCLE AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Figure 3 Circular Economy for the VideometerLite

In the TraceMyFish’s commitment to sustainability, a circular economy approach to production has been adopted. This not only benefits the environment but also promotes efficiency and longevity throughout the lifecycle of the instruments.

6.2.1 Raw Material, Design, Production and Distribution

Videometer adheres to the RoHS directive for the procurement of raw materials, ensuring that electronic parts are free from hazardous substances, and, thus, promoting the responsible sourcing of materials, safeguarding both human health and the environment.

The instruments are designed with a focus on robustness and durability. This not only extends their lifespan but also reduces the need for frequent replacements, minimizing waste and resource consumption.

Metal and plastic pieces are exclusively sourced in Europe, reducing the carbon footprint associated with international shipping and supporting local economies.

6.2.2 Use, Repair, Collection, Recycling

The instruments are designed to facilitate traceability and faster decision-making processes. This not only enhances efficiency but also contributes to more sustainable and data-driven business practices.

Service Level Agreements (SLAs) are put in place to provide support and repair services for the VideometerLab instruments. This promotes the repair and reuse of VideometerLab instrument components, reducing waste and extending the product's life.

When any Videometer instrument reaches the end of its usable life, the users are encouraged to return it to Videometer, which, then, ensures that the instruments are either recycled or their components reutilized, keeping valuable materials in circulation and out of landfills.

By implementing these circular economy principles, the TraceMyFish consortium aims at not only reduce the environmental impact linked to electronic manufacturing, but also contribute to a more sustainable and responsible approach to product development and consumption.

6.3 SDG ASSESSMENT

To further assess the TraceMyFish project's impact beyond the manufacturing and development processes, it was decided to look into the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The consortium's impact was measured by utilizing DNV's Self Assessment of SDGs with the Veracity Self Assessment Tool. The platform allows users to measure their influence on each of the SDG's targets by evaluating it as positive, negative or neutral, and assigning it a value.

The evaluation showed that TraceMyFish particularly impacts and has the potential to impact the following SDGs:

- SDG 2: Zero Hunger
- SDG 12: Responsible Production and Consumption
- SDG 14: Life Below Water
- SDG 17 Partnership for the Goals.

6.3.1 SDG 2: Zero Hunger

Sustainable Development Goal 2 aims at “ending hunger, achieving food security and improved nutrition and promoting sustainable agriculture”.

One of the main targets of SDG 2 is to achieve food safety across the globe, in order to ensure healthy nutritious food to all members of society, especially those in more vulnerable situations. The TraceMyFish project contributes to this cause by, not only, monitoring the seafood supply chain and the safety and quality of blue-

bio products, but also by ensuring faster decision-making processes in throughout the supply chain, which can aid in a more efficient food-waste management structure.

6.3.2 SDG 12: Responsible Production and Consumption

Sustainable Development Goal 12 aspires to “ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns”.

TraceMyFish impacts said goal, especially in regard to target 12.3, which states “by 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses”. As mentioned, before, in fact, the iFMS allows for time-efficient and responsible management of seafood products and by-products, leading to more sustainable production and waste practices.

Additionally, the TraceMyFish project commits to adopt circular economy practices for the manufacturing of the VideometerLite instrument. This encourages more efficient resource use, leading to reduced environmental impact and enhanced sustainability. The use of materials and resources is optimized to minimize waste, contributing to a more eco-friendly and economically efficient production process.

6.3.3 SDG 14: Life Below Water

SDG 14 aims at “conserving and sustainably using the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.”

One of the key ways in which the iFMS contributes to this goal is by actively reducing overfishing and promoting sustainable management practices in blue economies.

By offering advanced tools and insights, the iFMS aids in the sustainable management of fisheries. The system supports efficient waste management practices by tracking and minimizing discards, reducing waste and environmental impact.

In doing so, the iFMS fosters a more sustainable approach to the management of marine resources, contributing directly to SDG 14's objective of conserving and sustainably using the world's oceans, seas, and marine resources. Through these efforts, the iFMS aligns with the global mission to safeguard marine ecosystems and promote responsible blue economies, ensuring a healthier, more sustainable future for our oceans and the communities that rely on them.

6.3.4 SDG 17: Partnership for the Goals

SDG 17's goal is to “strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development”.

The TraceMyFish project actively promotes international partnerships, capacity building, and resource mobilization, aligning with the aims and objectives of SDG 17.

Supported by the European Union, this initiative brings together partners from different countries to advance blue bioeconomies. By uniting the expertise, resources, and knowledge of multiple countries, the project exemplifies the principles of global partnership.

In addition, within the TraceMyFish framework, capacity building activities play a relevant role. These activities include education, training, and skill development, which are fundamental for the pursuit of SDG 17.

Finally, international entities mobilize resources to support the project's objectives and promote sustainable blue economies. Such resource mobilization is essential for the financing and implementation of sustainable development initiatives, making a direct contribution to the goals of SDG 17.

7 MARKETING MIX

The Marketing Mix model, also commonly referenced as the 7Ps of Marketing, is a framework utilized to determine a company’s marketing strategies. (Borden, 1964). The model takes in consideration the following four commercial elements: product, price, place and promotion, and is further expanded by investigating contemporary marketing elements such as people, process and physical evidence (Booms & Bitner, 1982).

In the iFMS case, the model was established to be as follows:

Table 1 iFMS Marketing Mix

Element	Description
Product	iFMS (Comprised of Quantum, VideometerLite, VideometerLab Software inclusive of Videometer Global Workspaces).
Price	Cost-efficient solution, purchasable by all players on the seafood value chain.
Place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webshop, online sales on companies’ webpages. • Traditional sales with bank transfer
People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None • Traditional sales representatives
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User accesses webshop, purchases on-line with credit card, receives confirmation of order, product is physically shipped or download link is sent, invoice is sent. • User requests quote, sale representative configures quote based on user needs and desires, quote is accepted, purchase order is sent and accepted, invoice is sent, payment is made via bank transfer, product is shipped or download link is sent.
Physical Evidence	Peer-reviewed papers, conferences and deliverable by TraceMyFish partners. EU-funding itself. Quantum

	platform, VideometerLite instrument and VideometerLab Software.
Promotion	Website, social media organic and paid ads, industry events, customer testimonials.

8 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management tool used to develop, describe, and visualize a business model, it aids business in understanding and communicating how they intend to create value (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). The Business Model Canvas consists of nine key elements, which are arranged on a single page or canvas, making it easy to see how they interact and influence each other. Here are the nine building blocks:

1. **Customer segments:** the target audience of the business.
2. **Value proposition:** the unique value the business creates for its audience.
3. **Channels:** the channels through which the business reaches its customers segments.
4. **Customer relationships:** how the business interacts with its customer.
5. **Revenue streams:** sources of income for the company.
6. **Key resources:** essential assets, capabilities, know-hows of the company.
7. **Key activities:** most important actions the business must take to provide the product or service.
8. **Key partnerships:** the strategic partners of the business.
9. **Cost structure:** cost associated to the business.

The iFMS' Business Model Canvas can be summarized as follows:

The Customer Segments:

- **R&D and Research:** Serving research institutions and organizations engaged in seafood-related research and development.
- **Fish Processing:** Offering solutions to companies involved in processing seafood products.
- **Fish Harvesting:** Catering to businesses in the fish harvesting sector.
- **Retailers:** Providing services and products to retailers in the seafood industry.

Customer Relationships:

- **Co-creation:** Collaborating with customers to tailor solutions to their specific needs and challenges.
- **Automated Services:** Offering automated, self-service options for customers who prefer a headless approach.
- **Personal Services/Assistance:** Providing personalized support and assistance for customers who require guidance and expertise.

Channels:

- **Websites:** Utilizing online platforms for information dissemination, customer interaction, and sales.
- **Social Media:** Engaging with customers and the industry through various social media channels (Linkedin, Facebook, Twitter).

- Webshops/E-commerce: Offering an online marketplace for product sales and services.
- Industry Events: Participating in industry-related events and exhibitions to showcase instruments and platforms.
- E-learning/Online Calls: Providing online training and support to customers.

Value Propositions:

- Cost Efficient: Offering solutions that are acquirable by all players in the industry.
- Portable: Providing portable tools and systems for convenience and flexibility.
- Wireless: Embracing wireless technology for enhanced mobility and ease of use.
- AI-Driven: Leveraging artificial intelligence for data analysis and decision-making.
- Quality and Safety Analysis System: Ensuring quality and safety throughout the seafood value chain.

Key Activities:

- Production of VideometerLites: Manufacturing of VideometerLite products, including electronics, mechanics, optics, etc.
- Developing VideometerLab Software, Quantum and cloud solutions: Continuously developing and enhancing software for data analysis and management.
- Development of webshop: Creating and maintaining an online marketplace for product sales.
- Sales activities: Engaging in sales and marketing efforts to promote the iFMS.

Key Resources:

- Mechatronics: Utilizing expertise in mechatronics for product development.
- Software Development: Employing software developers to create and maintain the required applications.
- Cloud Development: Building and managing cloud-based systems for data storage and analysis.
- Database and analysis: Creating databases and analysis tools for customers.
- Sales and marketing: A dedicated team for sales and marketing activities.
- User Experience: Focusing on creating a user-friendly and efficient customer experience.
- Scientific Knowledge: Leveraging scientific knowledge from the TraceMyFish partners to support product development and data analysis.

Key Partners:

- Scio – Videometer: Industrial partners of the TraceMyFish consortium.
- AUA, NTNU, UoI, MATIS: Partnering with academic and research institutions for expertise and support.
- Suppliers: Engaging with suppliers of essential components.
- Programming Platforms: Utilizing programming platforms for software development.

- Database: Engaging with database providers for data storage and analysis.
- EU and National Entities: Involvement with the European Union and national entities.

Cost Structure:

- Value-Driven Cost Structure: Adopting a cost structure that aligns with the value offered to customers and the efficiency of operations, ensuring that resources are allocated wisely.

Revenue Streams:

- Fixed Listing Price: This revenue stream likely involves charging a set fee for listing or featuring products, services, or businesses on the iFMS platform. It can be a one-time fee for inclusion in a directory or marketplace or to promote specific offerings. This stream provides a direct source of income.
- Subscription Fee (Annual Fee): Subscriptions are a recurring revenue stream where customers pay an annual fee for continued access to the iFMS services, platform, or data. This revenue model provides predictable income and encourages customer retention, as subscribers typically receive ongoing benefits or access to exclusive features. It can be a reliable source of income for the project.
- Licenses: Licensing revenue may involve granting other businesses or organizations the right to use specific software, technology, or intellectual property developed by the TraceMyFish consortium. Licensing can generate income through one-time fees, royalties, or ongoing licensing agreements, depending on the terms of use. This stream can leverage the project's intellectual property to create value.

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scio – Videometer • AUA/NTNU/UoJ/MATIS • Plastic part suppliers • Camera/LED/Lenses suppliers • Microsoft Azure • Programming platforms • Database • EU/IFD 	<p>Key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of VMLites • Developing of Cloud/Quantum/Vm • Lab software • Development of webshop • Sales activities 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <p>Cost efficient, portable, wireless, AI-driven, quality and safety analysis throughout the seafood value-chain.</p>	<p>Customer Relationship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation • Automated services • Personal services/assistance 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D and research • Processing • Harvesting • Retailers
<p>Cost structure</p> <p>Value-driven cost structure</p>	<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechatronics • Software dev. • Cloud dev. • Database/analysis • Sales/Marketing • User experience • Scientific knowledge 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Websites • Social media • Webshops/E-commerce • Industry events • E-learning/on-line calls 	
		<p>Revenue streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fixed listing price • Subscription fee (annual fee) • Licenses 		

Figure 4 TraceMyFish Business Model Canvas

9 CONCLUSIONS

Task 8.2 aimed at developing a business model for the iFMS, so to be able to exploit the system commercially. The model is presented in the present deliverable, with a particular focus on building a strategy that is user-centric, sustainable, and profitable at the same time.

The iFMS is the combination of developments by industrial partners SCiO and Videometer. It includes the VideometerLite wireless and portable instrument, the VideometerLab Software with Global Workspaces and SCiO's data analysis platform Qvantum.

Each partner has investigated and determined its sales model and B2B strategy in terms of pricing and positioning, though focusing on similar user segments. SCiO carries on web-sale operations, with users contacting representatives for quotations based on their needs. Videometer focuses further on headless web-sales on an e-commerce platform. However, they both source their revenues from fixed listing prices, subscription fees and licensing agreements. The cost structure is value driven, leveraging on minimal costs to offer a price-efficient product to customers.

Additionally, a major focus of the Task and Deliverable 8.2 was the pursuit of a B2B strategy which embraces sustainable practices. The iFMS was ideated in the broader context of circular economy. In particular, the VideometerLite manufacturing process was thought so to be durable and robust for a longer product-life of the instrument and, thus, reducing the carbon footprint of production.

The iFMS also fits and relates to the United Nations' 2030 Sustainable Agenda – the system, because of its nature, is particularly relevant for a number of Sustainable Development Goals. Specifically, it pertains to goals 2 – Zero Hunger, 12 – Responsible Production and Consumption, 14 – Life Below Water and 17 – Partnership for the Goals, aiding not only the material pursuit of these goals, but also actively promoting the collaboration between international players.

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